

Canonical Modular Logarithm and Minimal Primitive Roots

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Abstract

We define a canonical modular logarithm f on the multiplicative group $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$ for any prime $k > 2$. Using this function, we show that among the generators modulo k , at least $\varphi(k-1)/2$ remain generators modulo k^n when $k > 3$, and that at least one exists when $k \leq 3$. We determine the general form of the sequence of orders modulo k^n for any integer coprime to k , and present several immediate properties of f . Additional extensions and algebraic remarks are also proposed.

Let $k > 2$ be a prime number. The multiplicative group $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$ is cyclic of order $\varphi(k^2) = (k-1)k$.

1. Definition of the Canonical Modular Logarithm

Let $k > 2$ be a prime number. We define the central function of this article:

Definition 1.1 (Canonical Modular Logarithm). The *canonical modular logarithm* is the function

$$f : (\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}$$

induced by the map

$$F : \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{k\mathbb{Z}\} \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}, \quad F(x) := \frac{x^{k-1} - 1}{k} \pmod{k}.$$

This function is well defined for any integer x coprime to k , since Fermat's little theorem gives $x^{k-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{k}$, so the numerator is divisible by k .

Proposition 1.2. The function F is constant on congruence classes modulo k^2 , and induces a well-defined map f on the group $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$.

Proof. If $x \equiv y \pmod{k^2}$, then $x^{k-1} - 1 \equiv y^{k-1} - 1 \pmod{k^2}$, and since both sides are divisible by k , we can take the quotient:

$$F(x) \equiv F(y) \pmod{k}.$$

$$f : (\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}, \quad f([x]) := F(x).$$

□

Proposition 1.3 (Multiplicative Compatibility). For all $x, y \in (\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$, we have:

$$f(xy) \equiv f(x) + f(y) \pmod{k}.$$

Proof. By definition,

$$f(x) = \frac{x^{k-1} - 1}{k}, \quad f(y) = \frac{y^{k-1} - 1}{k}, \quad f(xy) = \frac{(xy)^{k-1} - 1}{k}.$$

Now,

$$(xy)^{k-1} - 1 = x^{k-1}y^{k-1} - 1 = (x^{k-1} - 1)y^{k-1} + (y^{k-1} - 1).$$

Each term $x^{k-1} - 1$ and $y^{k-1} - 1$ is divisible by k , so the right-hand side is divisible by k , and we obtain:

$$f(xy) \equiv f(x) + f(y) \pmod{k}.$$

□

Proposition 1.4 (Properties of the function f). The function f satisfies the following properties:

1. f is a surjective group homomorphism;
2. f is independent of the choice of a generator of $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$; it is canonical;
3. If p is a primitive root modulo k , then $f(p) \not\equiv 0$ if and only if p is a primitive root modulo k^2 ;
4. For each class $\bar{p} \in (\mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z})^\times$, there exists a unique integer $m \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$ such that $f(p + mk) = 0$;
5. The kernel $\ker(f)$ is a subgroup of index k in $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$.

To prove (1), we only need to show surjectivity. Since $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$ is cyclic, let g be a generator of order $k(k-1)$. Then $f(g) \not\equiv 0$, and $f(g^m) \equiv mf(g) \pmod{k}$. Since $\gcd(f(g), k) = 1$, $f(g)$ is invertible in $\mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}$, hence f is surjective.

Property (2) simply reflects the lexical justification of the term "canonical".

For property (3), we will need the following lemma.

Lemma 1.5. If x has order α modulo k^t , then its order modulo k^{t+1} is either α or $k\alpha$.

Proof. Let β denote the order of x modulo k^{t+1} . Then

$$x^\beta \equiv 1 \pmod{k^{t+1}} \Rightarrow x^\beta \equiv 1 \pmod{k^t} \Rightarrow \alpha \mid \beta = \alpha m.$$

Now, since $x^\alpha \equiv 1 + \lambda k^t \pmod{k^{t+1}}$ for some $\lambda < k$, we have:

$$(1 + \lambda k^t)^m \equiv 1 + m\lambda k^t \pmod{k^{t+1}} \quad \text{for } t > 0.$$

Therefore,

$$m\lambda k^t \equiv 0 \pmod{k^{t+1}} \Rightarrow m\lambda \equiv 0 \pmod{k}.$$

If $\gcd(m, k) = 1$, then $k \mid \lambda$. Since $\lambda < k$, it follows that $\lambda = 0$, and therefore $x^\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{k^{t+1}}$.

Thus $\beta = \alpha$.

If $k \mid m$, then

$$(1 + \lambda k^t)^k \equiv 1 + \lambda k^{t+1} \pmod{k^{t+1}},$$

so $\beta \mid \alpha k \Rightarrow m \mid k$.

Hence $m = k$ and $\beta = \alpha k$. □

Proof. Let p be a primitive root modulo k , so its order modulo k is $k-1$. By the previous lemma, its order modulo k^2 is either $k-1$ or $k(k-1)$. Therefore, $f(p) \equiv 0 \Leftrightarrow \text{ord}(p, k^2) = k-1$. □

To prove Property 4, we examine the action of f on a residue class. Let $p \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus k\mathbb{Z}$ be fixed. Consider the function:

$$h : i \in \mathbb{Z} \mapsto f(p + ik) \in \mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}.$$

Using the binomial expansion:

$$(p + ik)^{k-1} = p^{k-1} + (k-1)p^{k-2} \cdot ik + \gamma k^2 \equiv p^{k-1} + (k-1)p^{k-2} \cdot ik \pmod{k^2},$$

we obtain:

$$f(p + ik) \equiv f(p) + (k-1)p^{k-2} \cdot i \pmod{k},$$

and hence:

$$f(p + ik) - f(p + jk) \equiv (k-1)p^{k-2}(i - j) \pmod{k},$$

so that:

$$f(p + ik) \equiv f(p + jk) \pmod{k} \iff i \equiv j \pmod{k}.$$

Thus, the function h is k -periodic. It is injective on the set $\{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$, which has the same cardinality as its image. It is therefore also surjective, and each value is attained exactly once. In particular, the value zero is attained exactly once per class in $(\mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z})^\times$, i.e., $k-1$ times in total.

Property 5 follows directly from classical results combined with the previous observation on the cardinality of the kernel.

2. Existence of a primitive root less than k

Lemma 2.1. Let p be a primitive root modulo k and a minimal representative of its class modulo k in $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$. Then its inverse modulo k^2 cannot also be the minimal representative of its class modulo k .

Proof. Indeed, if $1 < p < k$ and $1 < p^{-1} < k$, then $1 < pp^{-1} < k^2$ and $pp^{-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{k^2}$, which is a contradiction. \square

Theorem 2.2 (Existence of a primitive root less than k). For every prime number $k > 2$, there exists an integer $p < k$ which is a primitive root modulo k^n for all $n \geq 2$.

Proof. Let $\bar{p} \in (\mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z})^\times$ be a generator. Let p be its minimal representative in the interval $[1, k-1]$.

- If $f(p) \not\equiv 0$, then p is a primitive root modulo k^2 , and hence also modulo k^n for all $n \geq 2$ (see the lemma below).
- Otherwise, $f(p) \equiv 0$, so $p \in \ker(f)$, and thus $p^{-1} \in \ker(f)$ as well.

Let q be the minimal representative in $[1, k-1]$ of the inverse class $\bar{p}^{-1} \in (\mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z})^\times$. Since p is already a minimal representative in its class, we must have $p^{-1} \not\equiv q \pmod{k^2}$ (see Lemma 2), hence $q \notin \ker(f)$ (by the uniqueness of the zero of f in each class modulo k). Therefore, $f(q) \not\equiv 0$. Moreover, if p is a primitive root modulo k , then so are p^{-1} and q . Hence q is a primitive root modulo k^2 .

In both cases, we obtain a generator of $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$ strictly less than k . \square

Lemma 2.3 (Classical fact). Every primitive root modulo k^2 is a primitive root modulo k^n for all $n \geq 2$.

Although this result is classical, we include here a direct proof, based on a previously overlooked corollary.

Behavior of the order sequence modulo k^n

We have the following general relations:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{(k^{n+s})}$$

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^n} \equiv 1 + \lambda k^{n+s} \pmod{(k^{n+s+1})}$$

Proof. By induction.

The relation is obvious when $n = 0$, but we will also need the case $n = 1$:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^k = 1 + \lambda k^{s+1} + k^{2s} P(k)$$

Now $2s \geq s + 2 \Leftrightarrow s \geq 2$.

Assume:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^n} \equiv 1 + \lambda k^{n+s} \pmod{(k^{n+s+1})}$$

Then:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^{n+1}} = (1 + \lambda k^{n+s} + \mu k^{n+s+1})^k = 1 + k^{n+s+1}(\lambda + \mu k) + \gamma k^{\alpha(n+s)}$$

The condition $\alpha(n+s) \geq n+s+2$ is satisfied as soon as:

$$\alpha \geq \frac{n+s+2}{n+s} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{x+2}{x} = 1 + \frac{2}{x} \leq 2 \quad \text{whenever } x \geq 2$$

Thus, the condition holds as soon as $s \geq 2$. □

Lemma 2.4. If $s \geq 2$ and k is a prime that does not divide λ , then the order of $1 + \lambda k^s$ modulo k^{n+s} is exactly k^n .

Proof. The order of $1 + \lambda k^s$ modulo k^{n+s} divides k^n , so it is of the form k^m with $m \leq n$.

Assume:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^m} \equiv 1 \pmod{(k^{n+s})} \text{ with } m < n$$

Then:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^m} \equiv 1 \pmod{(k^{m+s+1})} \quad \text{since } m+s+1 \leq n+s$$

But:

$$(1 + \lambda k^s)^{k^m} \equiv 1 + \lambda k^{m+s} \pmod{(k^{m+s+1})}$$

So:

$$\lambda k^{m+s} \equiv 0 \pmod{(k^{m+s+1})} \Leftrightarrow \lambda \equiv 0 \pmod{(k)}$$

which is a contradiction. □

Lemma 2.5. Let p be coprime to k with order α modulo k :

$$p^\alpha = 1 + \mu k = 1 + \lambda k^s \quad \text{with } \gcd(\lambda, k) = 1$$

Then p has order αk^n modulo k^{n+s} , and order α modulo k^m for all $m \leq s$.

Proof. The second part follows immediately from the decomposition of p^α . Let us focus on the order modulo k^{n+s} .

From the previous result, p^α has order k^n modulo k^{n+s} .
Now, the order of p divides αk^n , so:

$$O(p) = \beta k^m \quad \text{with } \beta \mid \alpha \text{ and } m \leq n$$

$$p^{\beta k^m} \equiv 1 \pmod{(k^{n+s})} \Rightarrow p^{\beta k^m} \equiv 1 \pmod{(k)} \Rightarrow \alpha \mid \beta k^m$$

Since $\alpha \mid k - 1 \Rightarrow \gcd(\alpha, k) = 1$, we get $\alpha \mid \beta \Rightarrow \alpha = \beta$.

Therefore:

$$p^{\alpha k^m} \equiv 1 \pmod{(k^{n+s})} \Rightarrow k^n \mid k^m \Rightarrow n \leq m \Rightarrow n = m$$

□

Remark 2.6 (Special case: $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$). In this case, there are only two values of s of interest:

$$s = 1 \Leftrightarrow f(p) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{k^2} \Leftrightarrow O(p, k^2) = k \cdot O(p, k)$$

$$s = 2 \Leftrightarrow f(p) \equiv 0 \pmod{k^2} \Leftrightarrow O(p, k^2) = O(p, k)$$

Proposition 2.7. For any p coprime with k , the sequence $O(p, k^n)$ of the orders of $p \pmod{k^n}$ is stationary with value $\alpha = O(p, k)$ for s steps, and then becomes geometric with ratio k .

Remark 2.8. This result may be viewed as a generalization of classical observations on the growth of the multiplicative order of an integer. Traces of this phenomenon can be found in the historical literature, notably in Dickson's *History of the Theory of Numbers* (Vol. I, Chap. 4), where it is noted that the order may increase by a factor of k when moving from k^n to k^{n+1} , under certain divisibility conditions. However, the full recursive formulation established here does not appear to have been explicitly stated.

Proof of the existence of a primitive root modulo k^n

If p is a primitive root modulo k^2 , its order is $O(p, k^2) = k(k - 1)$. Then the sequence of its orders modulo k^n is geometric, namely $k^{n-1}(k - 1)$. Thus, all its representatives are primitive roots modulo k^n .

In fact, the above allows us to state the following result:

For every pair (p, p^{-1}) of primitive roots modulo k , at least one of the two standard representatives is a primitive root modulo k^n . These pairs form a partition of the set of generators modulo k whenever $p \not\equiv p^{-1}$. But $p \equiv p^{-1} \pmod{k} \Leftrightarrow p^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{k} \Leftrightarrow O(p, k) = 2 \Rightarrow k = 3$. Thus, for $k > 3$, there are at least $\varphi(k - 1)/2$ primitive roots modulo k^n strictly less than k .

Elementary Properties

The function f satisfies the following relations, all valid modulo k , for any $p \in \mathbb{Z}$:

1. (Notable value)

$$f(1 + k) \equiv -1$$

by direct application of the binomial theorem.

2. **(Shifted linearity)**

$$nf(p+k) \equiv (n-1)f(p) + f(p+nk)$$

for any integer n . Again, this follows from the binomial expansion.

3. **(Difference relation)**

$$f(p) - f(p+k) \equiv p^{-1}$$

obtained from the previous identity with $n = p$, using the first formula.

4. **(Periodic structure)** In particular, if $f(a) \equiv 0$, then:

$$f(a+nk) \equiv -na^{-1}$$

by direct application of the two preceding properties.

Decomposition of $\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z}$

Define an equivalence relation on $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$ by:

$$x \sim y \iff xy^{-1} \in \ker f$$

This partitions the group of units according to the values of f . Moreover, f is bijective on each residue class modulo k .

Therefore, any sequence of the form $x_n = a + nk$, for a fixed representative $a \in (\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$, describes the full set of values of f . In particular, choosing $a = 1$, any element x can be written as:

$$x = p(1 + nk)$$

with $p \in \ker f$, and then:

$$f(x) \equiv -n \pmod{k}$$

5. As a consequence, we obtain:

$$x \equiv p(1 - kf(x)) \pmod{k^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p \equiv x(1 + kf(x)) \pmod{k^2}$$

The second identity follows from the congruence:

$$(1 - kf(x))(1 + kf(x)) \equiv 1 \pmod{k^2}$$

Extensions and Perspectives

Natural extension to k^n . The construction leading to the logarithmic function f can be generalized to any power k^n by considering the identity

$$x^{k^n(k-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{k^{n+1}}.$$

This yields a function $f_{n+1} : (\mathbb{Z}/k^{n+2}\mathbb{Z})^\times \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}$ defined by

$$f_{n+1}(x) = \frac{x^{k^n(k-1)} - 1}{k^{n+1}} \pmod{k},$$

which inherits some of the properties of f , in particular its surjectivity and its role in identifying lifts of primitive roots. However, its action on residue classes modulo k is no longer trivial.

More generally, for any integer $1 \leq r \leq n+1$, one can define a family of multiplicative homomorphisms

$$f_r(x) = \frac{x^{k^n(k-1)} - 1}{k^r} \pmod{k^{n+2-r}},$$

with values in larger and possibly non-reduced rings. Although these functions are no longer surjective, their structure may allow for a finer analysis of the group $(\mathbb{Z}/k^{n+2}\mathbb{Z})^\times$. A detailed study of these maps remains open.

Perspectives

The canonical logarithm function f , defined on $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$, may hold structural interest beyond its role in the present results. Several directions can be envisaged to further explore its properties:

1. **Derived multiplicative morphisms.** Since f is a multiplicative homomorphism with values in $\mathbb{Z}/k\mathbb{Z}$, it is natural to consider compositions such as $\exp(2\pi i f(x)/k)$, with the aim of studying discrete characters constructed from f . One could then seek a formal analogy with the usual multiplicative characters, though here defined on a strict subgroup of $(\mathbb{Z}/k^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$.
2. **Extension to higher levels.** It would be interesting to explore generalizations of f to $(\mathbb{Z}/k^n\mathbb{Z})^\times$ for $n \geq 3$, aiming to define a canonical extension that preserves multiplicativity and vanishes on the classes that are not generators modulo k .

These extensions raise several natural questions: does the value spectrum of f reveal subtle divisibility properties? Does the structure of the kernel of f remain stable with increasing n ? Can one define a canonical discrete transform from f on the subgroup of generators? These open perspectives suggest that the function f deserves more systematic investigation.